

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Aromatic Acetals by Ceric Ammonium Nitrate in Acetonitrile Medium

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Aromatic acetals of benzaldehyde and substituted benzaldehydes with n-butanol have been prepared and subjected to ceric ammonium nitrate oxidation in acetonitrile medium. The oxidation follows a total second order kinetics, first order each in [acetal] and [Ce^{IV}]. Variation in ionic strength of the medium and added nitrate ions have no influence on the rate. Decrease of dielectric constant of the medium decreases the rate. Activation parameters have been computed from Arrhenius plots. Activation enthalpy and entropy of the oxidation are linearly related. Both activation energy and frequency factor have been found to control the reaction. A probable mechanism has been proposed.

A literature search revealed that though considerable attention has been focussed on the kinetics and mechanism of ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN) oxidations of a variety of organic compounds, similar work on CAN oxidation of aromatic acetals has not been reported so far. We report here a detailed study of the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of seven aromatic acetals in acetonitrile medium by CAN.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidation of acetals by Ce^{IV} were investigated under varying conditions. The oxidation reaction is found to be of first order with respect to the oxidant as proved by good fits of log absorbance vs time plot. But k_{obs} decreases with increase in the initial [Ce^{IV}]. But in each kinetic run, the reaction shows no deviation whatsoever from the first order plot. In view of this complexity, all subsequent experiments with the acetals have been carried out at the same concentration of oxidant for purposes of valid comparisons.

In cerium(IV) oxidations, the decrease of rate constant with increase in the initial concentration of the oxidant has been noted by many workers in different media¹⁻³. It is well established that cerium(IV) forms dimeric species in sulphuric acid^{2,4}, nitric acid^{5,6} and perchloric acid⁷ and trimeric species in acetic acid⁸. In addition to dimeric species polymeric species exist in nitric acid⁶. Prakash *et al.*⁹ explained the phenomenon on the assumption of possible formation of some less reactive polymeric cerium(IV) species at higher [Ce^{IV}]. The decrease of pseudo-first order rate constants with increase in initial [Ce^{IV}] in the present investigation is significant and may possibly be due to the formation of some less reactive polymeric cerium(IV) species at higher [Ce^{IV}] in a similar manner as in the instances cited above. The values of k_{obs} increase with increase in [acetal]

and $k_{obs}/[\text{acetal}]$ are constant pointing to first order dependence on substrate.

It is known that complex formation between cerium(IV) and the substrate depends upon both the anions associated with cerium(IV) and the substrate and steric effects hinder complex formation⁹.

The substrates in the present investigation have alkyl groups directly bonded to the ligating oxygen atoms and should naturally hinder complex formation, that too when there are *gem*-dialkoxy groups in the acetals. As such the kinetics of the present investigation is not of the Michaelis-Menten type. Hence order with respect to acetal is unity.

Effect of ionic strength: Variation in ionic strength of the medium was effected with sodium perchlorate. It was found that the rate of oxidation of acetal with cerium(IV) was not influenced by the ionic strength of the medium. This rules out an ion-ion interaction. Hence the reaction may be between an ion and a neutral molecule or between two neutral molecules.

Effect of added tetraethylammonium nitrate (TEAN): The purpose of studying the effect of TEAN is two-fold: (i) to observe the effect of changing the ionic strength and (ii) to observe the effect of changing the concentration of nitrate ions. In the present study, TEAN does not influence the rate of oxidation thereby ruling out both the above effects.

The absence of the effect of ionic strength is also in line with observations made under the effect of added sodium perchlorate in the present study. The absence of the effect of added nitrate ions observed on the kinetics in the present study is quite contrary to the effect observed in the oxidation of α -hydroxy acids by CAN¹⁰ in which case k_{obs} decreases with increasing [NO₃⁻]. A bidentate complex is formed between reactive cerium(IV) species and the α -hydroxy acid by displacing a

nitrate ion maintaining the coordination number 12. An increase in the concentration of nitrate ion should act in the reverse direction, i.e. the nitrate ion displacing the complexing substrate thereby decreasing the k_{obs} . In the present investigation no retarding effect of nitrate ions is observed. This is possible in the case where no exchange of nitrate ligands by the substrate takes place. The absence of complex formation may be inferred from this effect also.

Effect of solvent polarity on reaction rate: With decrease in the dielectric constant of the medium effected by addition of carbon tetrachloride, the rate was found to decrease. With the increase of percentage of carbon tetrachloride in the binary solvent mixture the polarity of the solvent decreases. If the transition state is more polar than the reactants it will be stabilised by more polar solvents thus accelerating the reaction. The reaction is accelerated by increase in polarity of the solvent mixture. Hence the transition state may be more polar than the reactants. A plot of $\log k_2$ vs $(D-1)/(2D+1)$ is linear indicating the involvement of two neutral molecules. This inference can explain more polar transition state than the reactants. This inference is in agreement with the little effect of the ionic strength of the medium on the rate of oxidation.

Acetals are known to exist in ionic form due to protonation in acid medium¹¹. Acetonitrile is a weaker base¹² and much weaker acid¹³ than water. Therefore in acetonitrile acetals will exist as neutral species.

In the present study, the effect of solvent indicates that the reaction is between two neutral species. Hence a neutral species of cerium(IV) may be reactive. Several complexes represented by $[Ce(NO_3)_n]^{4-n}$, where n has an integral value between 1 and 6, are known¹⁴. In the present investigation, the reactive cerium(IV) species may possibly be $Ce(NO_3)_4$. $Ce(NO_3)_4$ has been reported to be the reactive cerium(IV) species in the cerium(IV) oxidation of formaldehyde¹⁵. Recently, a neutral species, namely, $Ce(SO_4)_2$ has been reported to be the reactive form of cerium(IV) in the oxidation of maltose and lactose by ceric ammonium sulphate in sulphuric acid solution¹⁶.

Effect of added *n*-butyl benzoate: In the oxidation of benzaldehyde di-*n*-butyl acetal (BnBA) the kinetic runs with initially added *n*-butyl benzoate (one of the products) gave rates which were identical with those obtained in the absence of ester. This indicates that (i) the ester formed in the oxidation of acetal is not undergoing oxidation under the experimental conditions in the present study and (ii) the ester formation takes place in a fast step. The possibility of free radical mechanism is inferred as the oxidation of BnBA with CAN induced the polymerisation of acrylonitrile.

Effect of substituents in the benzene ring of

aldehyde moiety: Hammett's correlations on the oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted acetals (Table 1) show a negative ρ value ($\rho = -0.89$ at 313 K; $r=0.98$) for the reaction. The negative ρ suggests that a small amount of positive character develops on the benzylic carbon of the aldehyde moiety of the acetal molecule in the transition state. This is not uncommon because the cerium(IV) system is electrophilic and would therefore induce an electron deficiency in the transition state^{17,18}. It is known that the oxidative cleavage of alcohols by cerium(IV) appears to proceed via a polar transition state, wherein a fair amount of positive charge delocalises on the radical which is being formed¹⁹.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_{obs}) FOR OXIDATION OF AROMATIC ACETALS

[Acetal] = 2×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³, [CAN] = 1×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, Solvent = 100% CH₃CN, Temp. = 313 K

Acetal	k_{obs} $\times 10^4$ s ⁻¹
BnBA	0.91
4-CH ₃	1.35
4-Cl	0.58
3-Cl	0.60
3-NO ₂	0.24
4-NO ₂	0.17

Rho values reported²⁰⁻²⁵ for benzyl radical reactions are in the range -0.3 to -1.5 . Rho values reported²⁶ for benzyl cation processes are in the range -4.5 to -6.5 . Most radical reactions do not exhibit excellent Hammett correlations and give rho values in the range^{20,22,24} -0.5 to -1.5 . In the present investigation the involvement of radicals is inferred from the induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile.

The rates of oxidation were obtained at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). The oxidation of all the acetals were found to have negative values for the

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Acetal	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
BnBA	34.3	31.7	-188.8	90.8
4-CH ₃	32.9	30.3	-190.2	89.8
4-Cl	46.3	43.7	-154.2	92.0
3-Cl	35.6	33.0	-188.1	91.9
3-NO ₂	36.5	33.9	-192.9	94.3
4-NO ₂	62.1	59.5	-113.6	95.1

entropy of activation. This suggests a restriction to the freedom of movement of the two species, namely, acetal and cerium(IV). This may possibly be explained by the transition state involving both oxidant and acetal, which is likely to be more solvated due to increased charge separation. From the linearity of the plot of $\log A$ vs $1/E_a$ it may be inferred that both activation energy and frequency factor control the reaction ($r=0.98$). Closeness of ΔG^\ddagger values indicates that all the acetals are oxidised by an identical mechanism.

The changes in the rate of oxidation of aromatic acetals by cerium(IV) are governed by changes in both enthalpy and entropy of activation, which is shown by the linear correlation between the activation enthalpy and entropy ($r=0.99$).

Mechanism: Based on the results the rate law may be as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k [\text{acetal}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$$

In the light of the study the mechanism may be explained by Scheme 1. However, it may be pointed out that in the case of 4-methoxybenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal the reaction was too fast to be measured conveniently. Similar phenomena have been observed in the Ce^{IV} oxidative cleavage of 1,2-diarylethanols²⁷ and in the Ce^{IV} oxidation of substituted benzyl alcohols¹⁸. It is concluded that the 4-methoxy substituent activates the aromatic ring suggesting that a different mechanism must operate.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Acetonitrile (E. Merck) was purified as reported elsewhere²⁸. BnBA, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 3-nitrobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 3-chlorobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 4-methylbenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal and 4-methoxybenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal were prepared by the standard methods²⁹ and the purity was checked by the usual methods.

Kinetic measurements: The reaction was carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ($[\text{acetal}] \gg [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$) in acetonitrile and followed colorimetrically at 420 nm (Erma AE-11S). The validity of Beer's law was checked for the entire range of $[\text{oxidant}]$ used. Cerium(IV) on reduction gives colourless cerium(III). Hence there was no interference from the reduced form of the oxidant. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed from the linear ($r > 0.98$) plots of log absorbance against time. The results are reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Product analysis: The glc analysis of the products of the oxidation of BnBA showed the presence of n-butylbenzoate and 1-butene. It was observed that 2 mol of oxidant consumed 1 mol of BnBA. The observed stoichiometries may be represented as

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